

Tactical Autonomic Language for 5G Network Management

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Abstract—this paper describes a Tactical Autonomic Language (TAL) for Self-Organizing Networks (SON)-enabled autonomic management of 5G networking infrastructures. The TAL is represented in the form of an XML Schema, and its information model is defined through an XSD.

The paper presents the TAL aiming at describing the language as the means to define autonomic behaviors in terms of system reaction to certain network issues by presenting the main principles of the TAL concept and the information model. The information regarding the inclusion of TAL processing in development work is presented.

Keywords— *Tactical Autonomic Language; Self-Organizing Networks; autonomic management; 5G*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Tactical Autonomic Language (TAL) here described is part of the H2020 5G PPP SELFNET project [1] architecture [2]. It was defined by taking into account the project use cases as well as the various workflows required to provide Self-Organizing Networks (SON)-enabled autonomic management of 5G networking infrastructure, and it is largely represented in the form of an XML Schema, being its information model defined through an XSD, which addresses extensibility needs with respect to definitions of application types and orchestration abstraction and aggregation and analysis processes.

Human experience is expressed by the definition of certain reactions by means of deployment of additional sensing and actuation functionalities to a number of detectable conditions that can be expressed by a combination of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Health of Network (HoN) metrics. The association of conditions with reactions is expressed in tactics, and SELFNET framework targets the provision of a machine learning framework that will optimize human defined tactics over time so as to maintain and augment a more precise and accurate Self-Organizing mode of operation. The TAL is an essential element of this approach.

The definition of the TAL was based on a process of abstracting the architecture, interfaces and workflow details in a way that can be aligned with the autonomic operation concepts without imposing restrictions to the inclusion of future aspects.

The primary objective of the TAL is to facilitate a formal definition of the autonomic behaviors in the SELFNET framework based on:

- Expandable syntax that aligns with the layering of the SELFNET architecture
- Definition and taxonomy of semantics for the expression of several SON aspects and of the processing that is required to be applied at the various layers

This paper is based on the results presented in SELFNET's D5.1 - Report and Software Libraries to deal with the Tactical Autonomic Language, and the section on the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine of D5.4 - Report of the Planner Module [3].

II. TACTICAL AUTONOMIC LANGUAGE (TAL) APPROACH

The TAL definition addresses not only generic aspects of diagnosis and reaction procedures but also other aspects presented in the context of workflows of other modules of the network management architecture, trying to consider all the heterogeneous requirements posed by almost all the layers of the architecture. The approach towards the resolution of such complex dependencies was based on the initial principle of maintaining extensibility and abstraction in the TAL syntax and models.

A TAL based reaction to a situation is defined as a TAL script. The term situation is used to describe the outcome of the monitoring, aggregation and analysis processing over a set of raw sensor data generated by any kind of information source either installed as an infrastructure functionality or being part of an End-to-End Network Service (E2E-NS) composition.

The various action plans (tactics), foreseen to overcome particular causes, are specialized by a number of parameters that are considered to be available either as raw or enriched data information obtained from the monitoring sublayer or as the outcome of a particular control loop phase in the context of the current symptom-cause-tactic processing phases.

III. CONCEPT

The TAL is part of the SON-Based Autonomic Management Engine layer, expressing a set of tactical strategies to specify the human-based tactical approaches regarding the reactions of the system in view or detection of

certain events and anomalies in the system being controlled. These strategies will still be algorithmically processed by the artificial intelligence to produce optimal decisions.

In the context of this autonomic management framework, TAL constitutes the static definition of the intelligence, usually incorporating experience of network management personnel, providing the initial starting point where the common sense intended behavior is expressed and that may thereafter be optimized by the artificial intelligence based processing.

A. *Diagnosis*

Although the term ‘diagnosis’ relates to conditions that may be considered problematic, it has been used in the autonomic language in order to indicate the process of associating information obtained from the monitoring components with the identification of a possible problem and its potential root causes.

TAL identifies an information model according to which diagnosis embraces all potential input such as those received from sensors in terms of events or raw data, aggregation of sensor data, analysis of aggregated data including Key Performance Indicator (KPI) metrics, and even more advanced Health of Network (HoN) metrics produced at the end of the processing and correlation procedures.

1) *Symptoms*

The process of diagnosis is triggered by the appearance of a symptom as an indication coming from the monitoring and analysis components. A symptom is defined as a concept to express the combination of qualitative and quantitative values that are produced according to a defined set of rules. The rules address aggregation procedures, KPIs and HoN metrics, analysis processes or even raw data coming directly from sensing sources.

The diagnostic components are being informed during runtime in the context of reports about KPIs and HoN metrics that may have been included in the definition of various symptoms. As long as all the metrics, qualitative (detection of particular flow or pattern) or quantitative (sensor values above a certain threshold) relating to symptom have been observed, the symptom is considered to be active. From the moment a symptom is detected the potential cause or causes that may have made the symptom appear are evaluated as potential situations to be tackled with.

2) *Causes*

Causes are defined in order to annotate in a human conceivable way a number of potential situations that lead to performance metrics which, according to the SON principles, need special attention so that resolution or optimisation measures are applied. A cause appears in TAL as an index that aids in decision making and it is of importance to the autonomic processing in the process of intelligence building.

Based on experience accumulated in the process of dealing with certain symptoms, the cause ranking and more specific or additional causes are expected to be updated to reflect the progress and the evolution in the intelligent processing and machine learning mechanisms.

B. *Decision Making and Reaction*

Assuming that the diagnosis process has concluded to deal with a particular set of causes, a strategy needs to be applied in order to follow the tactical approach defined in TAL. TAL allows for the definition of a set or sets of actions to be enforced. In the same way that the detection of a cause in view of a symptom is enabled as a process of deciding among the most possible one from those initially identified or others that can be later on added through machine learning or further manual input, this is also enabled for the case of resolving which set of actions to enforce.

Based on the administrator experience, action sets per cause are ranked from the most applicable to the less applicable or from the most common practice to the most peculiar.

In order for the decision making process to become more accurate in future reactions, there is need for potentially identifying the purpose of an action included in a set of actions. The purpose in TAL is expressed in a similar way the symptoms have been expressed. Thus, an action may be accommodated by an intended symptom that is expected to be detected in the near future as a result of the action enforced. This approach implies that there is a certain degree of statefulness in the operation of the autonomous management where any enforced action is correlated with future output of the monitoring and analysis components. In case the purpose of the action is verified when the decision was made, these situations may be potentially used to elevate or lower the applicability of the certain action with respect to the management of a certain cause or even symptom.

The TAL defines diagnosis and reaction behaviours as the starting point of the intelligence and machine learning based processing of the autonomous management.

C. *Monitoring Definitions*

All the data provided from virtual or physical resources, such as VNF or SDN Apps, SDN Controller Apps, Infrastructure probes or any other means of monitor sources are referred to as sensor data. It is expected that sensor data (specific output parameter of sensor type) may be indicated in a symptom definition apart from the output of higher level components such as aggregator or analyser.

1) *KPI Metrics*

TAL identifies a number of potential aggregation rules expressed as functions to be applied to specific raw data or even to intermediate output from several aggregation steps. Time related information (interval, frequency, etc.) may be also defined. Metrics can be, alike raw sensor data, included in the definition of a symptom. In case that KPI calculation involves more complex processing that cannot be defined by a combination of several aggregation steps, TAL allows the possibility of indicating an aggregation rule not only by using a dedicated function but also by use of an aggregation rule identifier. In this case, during runtime, the input parameters as expressed by output values from sensor data have to be mapped and sent to a software component relating to the identifier. This approach is defined as the plugin mechanism that may refer either to loadable software libraries or to future released

functionality that cannot be apparently included in TAL predefined rules. This capability confers TAL an additional extensibility to support dynamic on-boarding of new ways of performing data aggregations.

2) HoN Metrics

Whilst KPIs are relatively easier to obtain or derive at the aggregation level, HoN metrics introduced by SELFNET are more advanced high-level indicators of system performances and are able to facilitate deriving more direct and relevant, HoN-based symptoms, which in turn would facilitate the diagnosis. An example of a SELFNET HoN metric is the Quality of Experience (QoE) of a video application end user. This QoE HoN metric directly reflects the perceived quality of the end user, in contrast to traditional network-level Quality of Service (QoS) metrics or KPIs. Therefore, the modelling of an HoN metric is expected to require a more complex processing of the lower-level metrics including relevant KPIs and other aggregated metrics and/or raw metadata.

Since deriving an HoN metric needs more complex processing of a number of metrics based on a predefined model or pattern, it is foreseen that a HoN plugin can be identified in TAL relating to the proper implementation of the way to achieve HoN-based data analysis so that it can be activated and fed with any metric or sensor parameters for applying a more complex processing, the output of which is used in the diagnosis process.

D. Action Definitions

TAL allows the definition of a number of actions depending on the availability of these action types at the time a script is being defined. For each type of action, a configuration set may be required so that the action is properly applied. Configuration parameters have a well-defined type so that appropriate mapping or values are applied during runtime. There are different possible action options:

1) Sensor Action Type

TAL allows the administrator to indicate any particular type of sensing that may be required so that additional symptoms can be detected and a second loop of more accurate reaction can be activated.

2) Actuator Action Type

Actuator actions are expected to be the most common reaction to certain causes. Similar to sensors, actuator actions are expected to be of specific types that are also configured via parameters the type of which is also well defined.

3) Resource Action Type

Actions regarding resources do not require the existence of any application to be instantiated. The actions are expected to be followed to the resource manager component where lifecycle, scaling and migration tasks can be accommodated.

E. Bootstrapping Definitions

Apart from correlating actions in the context of tactics, TAL may play an additional role with respect to the bootstrapping of the platform for initial provisioning of basic functionalities. In this context, TAL can define a number of

actuators, sensors, network services and end-to-end network services to be deployed across the infrastructure. This is similar to the provisioning of sensors included in monitoring and aggregation definitions and are not part of any reaction. Finally, TAL can be used to define aggregation rules that can be then linked with the KPI or HoN metrics that are required for the identification of symptoms.

F. TAL Control Loop

The configuration parameters for the various action options of a tactic include either direct values (e.g. numerical) or references to information processed in previous steps of the control loop as explicitly stated in the TAL script defining the processed symptom. References can be also defined between action steps of the same tactic so that it is possible to configure one action option with information that was made available after the successful orchestration of a previous action step.

Figure 1: TAL control loop

As seen in Figure 1, the Action Enforcement component receives the identifier of the tactic to be applied and uses it to retrieve the TAL script from the TAL repository in order to resolve the runtime values of the configuration parameters that have to be provided to the Orchestrator in order to enforce the action plan. More specifically, the tactic definition includes a number of ordered action options. Each of these options can be a choice among sensing type action, actuation type action, or resource related actions.

IV. STRUCTURE

A. TAL Schema

The TAL is defined as an XML Schema (XSD). The language is used to express the relationship among the various elements managed in the SELFNET framework and all the required processing steps involved from data collection to action enforcement, meaning that TAL definitions affect various parts of the framework.

The concepts managed in TAL foresee the need of the existence of unique identifiers for such concepts such as action types, application types and parameter types. The reason for this design approach is at least twofold. First and most important, the identifiers are used to perform a unique and unambiguous mapping between parameters and configuration fields so that incoming information from the monitoring and analysis components can be properly used as input in the processes of action enforcing and orchestration. Additionally, a

certain degree of flexibility is achieved with respect to selection and definition of sensing and actuation choices. This flexibility comes by the independent nature of the actual implementation due to the fact that the autonomic definitions can be focused on the type of actions to be performed or the data to be monitored among all the choices rather than bidding them to particular implementation details

Unique identifiers in TAL are presented either as element attributes (OID="...") or as dedicated elements (<OID>...</OID>).

B. TAL Library and Database

The definition of bootstrapping and reactions in TAL are done in the form of XML files according to the XML schema of TAL information model. The unmarshalling of the stored data during runtime is handled via the use of Java based TAL library that can parse the XML definitions and produce runtime information structures that can be integrated with the application logic of various components. The same library can be used for the reverse purposes of producing XML files from information structures that are produced in memory during runtime. The later caters for TAL script generation and modification.

The TAL XML files are stored in an XML database. The advantage of the XML databases is that they allow XQUERY expressions to be processed that in turn produce views of TAL definitions from different perspectives. For example, aggregation rules defined in a bootstrapping section might have to be listed independently of other sections so that the aggregation engine can be configured accordingly. Similarly, the sensor indications of the aggregation data sections can be collected to prepare monitoring components with respect to the interaction with particular sensors.

V. TAL-BASED ACTION ENFORCEMENT ENGINE

The TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine resides on the Action Enforcer (AE) module of the SELFNET framework, as presented in figure 2.

Fig.2. SELFNET Action Enforcer Module

The AE translates the tactics previously identified into a set of action plans by making use of the AE's TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine. Action plans are sent to the Orchestrator module, which will translate them into low level (fine-granularity) actions for their final deployment and enforcement in the virtualized and physical network resources, in order to

fix the problem identified or even to be proactive so as to prevent subsequent problems.

The AE validates, organizes and refines the information by means of applying conflict detection and language refining techniques based on the TAL library definitions, in order to provide an implementable plan ready to be enforced in the network.

A. TAL-based AE Operation Procedure

The detailed operation procedure with respect to the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine is comprised by the following steps:

1. Tactics are reported to the AE through the Decision Making API.
2. AE forwards these tactics as well as the corresponding configuration of each action to the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine.
3. AE receives from the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine the set of actions, being translated from the tactics, together with the configuration of the previous step.
- In parallel to the last step, as seen in Figure 3, two more steps are carried out within AE beyond the limits of the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine:
 4. Actions suggested by the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine are also sent to ASE to be analyzed so as to avoid conflicts in a further deployment and enforcement.
 5. These actions are scheduled by ASE, which sends the highest priority action as an action plan to the Orchestrator through the Orchestrator API shown in Figure 3.

Fig.3. SELFNET AE main Control loop

VI. TACTICS AND ACTION PLANS FOR THE PRIMARY SCENARIO OF EACH UC

In SELFNET several scenarios have been defined in the context of three main use cases for demonstrating emerging network problems in 5G networks:

A. Self-Healing UC

The Self-Healing UC scenario is the "Resource failure prediction based proactive live migration of VMs". The UC is devoted to maintain normal operations of the 5G networks in a proactive way by monitoring energy distribution system, such as power output, rack conditions or temperature fluctuations, and enforcing certain responses to solve problems or malfunctions before they become critical, or even before they can lead to a serious outage.

B. Self-Protection UC

For the Self-Protection UC the scenario is called "DDoS attacks conducted by a botnet", and it is concerned with detecting 5G subscribers compromised and recruited within a botnet to launch DDoS attacks, as well as mitigating their

consequences in terms of network congestion or QoS degradation. This is conducted in a proactive and reactive way (i.e., before the cyber-attack is performed or during its execution, respectively).

Figure 4: TAL-based tactics and action plans available for AE regarding each UC

C. Self-Optimization UC

The scenario of the Self-Optimization UC, called "Video streaming in changing network environment using a 5G Hot Spot", is concerned with delivering video stream to 5G subscribers with sustained users' QoE. Through a Media-Aware Network Element (MANE) actuator, this scenario aims to maintain, or at least minimize, the disruption of the users' QoE in the case of network congestion, amongst other issues, likely to be happened in 5G networks.

Concrete tactics and action plans were defined for these scenarios. A pool of tactics and action plans for the presented scenario of each UC is shown in Figure 4.

The way of extracting tactics and action plans can be done through the SELFNET TAL library [3]. The TAL library is generated from the XML schema definition. For any element defined in the TAL, the library provides a Java Factory class that can be used to parse any extract of XML containing the defined element.

Once actions have been gathered by the TAL-based Action Enforcement Engine, they are sent to ASE with the aim of being scheduled and prepared to be sent to the Orchestrator through the defined Orchestrator API.

The current paper doesn't cover the tactics and action plans associated with each of the UCs due to length limitation but this information can be found in [3] and [5] for the main scenario of each UC:

For all scenarios, the source scripts in TAL have been defined in [3] and in SELFNET D5.3 - Report and Prototypical Implementation of the Integration of the Algorithms and Techniques Used to Provide Intelligence to the Decision-Making Framework [5], where the tactics and the action plans used by the AE as input and output, respectively, are detailed.

VII. CONCLUSION

The TAL here presented has evolved through a continuous process of accommodating several aspects of the SELFNET

infrastructure [1]. All the definitions progressed according to extensibility and abstraction principles that have played a main role in introducing several other concepts.

The TAL focused initially on accommodating autonomic concepts imposed mainly from machine learning principles. Additionally, aggregation and analysis aspects also became part of TAL concepts and plugin mechanisms were introduced to maintain extensibility.

The Action Enforcer applies conflict detection and language refining techniques based on the TAL library definitions to provide an implementable plan ready to be enforced in the network, playing a key role in translating the information provided to the module, validating, organizing and refining it.

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